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Analysis of brand relationship, brand personality, brand loyalty through brand commitment on products bang fish in Medan city

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Abstract

Brand loyalty is a form of emotional and rational attachment of consumers to a brand, which is reflected in consumers' preference to continue to buy products or services from the brand. The purpose of this study is to partially analyze brand relationships, brand personality, and brand loyalty through brand commitment to bang fish products in Medan City. The population is customers of bang fish products in the city of Medan which amounted to 196 respondents. The data collection method is by distributing questionnaires. The data analysis method used is structural equation modeling-partial least squares (SEM-PLS) using SmartPLS software 4. The results of the study show that all the results of the significant influence between Brand Relationship affect Brand Loyalty, Brand Relationship affect Brand Commitment, Brand Personality affect Brand Loyalty, Brand Personality affect Brand Commitment, Brand Commitment has a positive effect on Brand Loyalty, Brand Commitment significantly mediates the relationship between Trialability and Brand Loyalty, Brand Commitment significantly mediates the relationship between Brand Relationship and Brand Loyalty, Brand Commitment significantly mediates the relationship between Brand Personality and Brand Loyalty.

Keywords: Brand Relationship; Brand Personality; Brand Loyalty; Brand Commitment

1. Introduction

In the midst of increasingly competitive global market dynamics, brand loyalty is one of the key aspects in maintaining business sustainability. Brand loyalty is a very important component of a long-term marketing strategy. Brand loyalty is a measure of customer association with a brand [1] Brand loyalty is a form of emotional and rational attachment of consumers to a brand, which is reflected in consumers' preference to continue buying products or services from the brand, even though there are various alternative options in the market. Research by [2] in [3] shows that a 5% increase in consumer loyalty can increase a company's profitability by 25% to 95%. This fact shows that brand loyalty has direct implications for the financial success of a company. In the midst of the development of social media and e-commerce, consumers' perception of brands depends not only on the quality of the product, but also on their experience in interacting with the brand as a whole.

Consumers can easily compare products between brands, read reviews from other consumers, and search for cheaper or better alternatives to suit their needs. As a result, many brands are facing challenges in retaining their consumers, as brand loyalty is increasingly fragile amid increasing competition and rapidly changing consumer preferences. For example, bang fish products. For predatory fish hobbyists, especially channa fish. The name bang fish is familiar. Almost all hobbyists know it. Bang fish products are fish feed for predatory fish, especially channa fish. Channa fish or commonly called snakehead fish has been increasing in prestige for the past few years [4] This is an opportunity for bang fish in the midst of the channa fish phenomenon and can benefit modern businesses in the midst of a very rapid development of the times like today.

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Seeing the importance of brand loyalty in the context of modern business, this research is expected to make a theoretical and practical contribution in understanding and analyzing Brand Relationship, Brand Personality, and Brand Loyalty through Brand Commitment to Bang Fish products in Medan City

2. Literature Review

2.1. Brand Relationship

According to [5] Brand Relationship is a relationship over time between consumers and a brand that makes consumers consume the brand repeatedly. The Dimension of Brand Relationship According to [6] in [7] there are 8 Dimensions of Brand Relationship, namely: (1). Trust in the brand (Trust) (2). Satisfied with the brand (Satisfied) (3). Considers the company to be consistent with transactions and product performance (Consistent). (4). Consider the company to be easily accessible. (5) Consider the company responsive. (6) The company is committed to customers and puts them first (Committed). (7) Have affinity for the company and other customers (Affinity), (8) Like the company and enjoy doing business with the company (Like).

The Brand Relationship Indicator According to [8] in [9] there are 4 indicators in Brand Relationship, namely: (1). Interdependence: the extent to which the brand penetrates into the customer's daily life, both behaviorally. (2). Self-Concept Connection: the extent to which the brand provides an important identity, a sense of necessity, a theme, thus expressing a significant part of the self-concept, both in the past (a reference to nostalgia and memories of the Brand) and the present, personal and social. (3). Love/passion: Attraction and adoration of the brand, in various alternatives. (4). Intimacy: a deep feeling of familiarity and also an understanding of the essence of the brand as a partner in the relationship and the characteristics of the brand relationship between customers and the brand.

2.2. Brand Personality

One part of the strength of the brand is created to introduce products and maintain them in the market. [10] in [11] defines brand personality as "the specific mix of human traits that we can attribute to a particular brand" which means that brand personality is a certain mix of human traits that we can attribute to a particular brand. This human nature is the foundation for the formation of brand personality. In brand personality, there are dimensions that influence its formation. Aaker in [12] said that the five main dimensions of brand personality are Sincerity (sincerity), Excitement (interest), Competence (competence), Shopistication (worldliness), Ruggedness (durability). To measure the formation of a brand personality or not, it must be measured by the dimensions and indicators of this brand personality. According to Aaker in [13] brand personality has 5 elements, namely sincerity, excitement, competence, Sophistication, and Ruggednes.

2.3. Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty or brand loyalty is a commitment that is firmly held to buy back or become a repeat customer of a product or service that is consistently liked by [14] in ([15] According to [1] brand loyalty is a relationship between customers and a brand. This measure gives an idea of whether or not a customer may switch to another brand offered by a competitor, especially if the brand is found to have a difference in price or other attributes. Brand loyalty develops following four stages, namely cognitive, affective, conative and action. The four stages are [14] in [16] (1). Cognitive Loyalty is the main dimension. The focus on this dimension is product quality which can affect customer preferences, product cost as well as product knowledge. (2) Affective Loyalty as the second most important dimension. This dimension shows customer satisfaction and pleasure with products from the same brand. (3). Conative Loyalty is the desire to repurchase in this dimension as a reaction to a positive attitude towards a certain brand. (4). Behavioral Loyalty shows the frequency of customer repeat purchases. How regularly customers buy products from a particular brand.

According to [17] the factors that affect brand loyalty to consumers are (1). Value of price and quality of the brand, (2). Brand reputation and characteristics, (3). Comfort and ease of getting a brand, (3). Satisfaction, (4). Ministry, (5). Warranty or guarantee. The indicators of brand loyalty [18] in [19] propose five indicators of brand loyalty as follows: (1) Repeat purchase intention is the behavior of consumers to buy the same product or service again at the same company. (2) Self-stated retention behavior when the consumer promises himself to be loyal to the company. (3) Price insensitivity behavior when consumers do not pay much attention to price problems. (4) Resistance to counter persuasion behavior when consumers are not influenced by the persuasion of competitors' brands. (5) Spreading positive recommendations (likelihood of spreading positive word of mouth) behavior where consumers are satisfied and want to recommend positive things about products or services to others.

2.4. Brand Commitment

Brand Commitment is a sustainable consumer tendency in the purchasing relationship with a company/brand. According to [20] in [21] commitment is the consumer's continuous desire to continue the relationship with the service provider accompanied by the willingness to make efforts in maintaining it. Commitment is a very important asset for companies to establish long-term and mutually beneficial relationships with each other, or it can be said that commitment is closely related to consumer loyalty. Factors Brand commitment is explained by Mowday and McDade (1979) in [22] as follows (1). Strong conviction and acceptance of brand goals and values, (2). The willingness to exert sufficient effort on behalf of the brand, and (3). A strong desire to keep a brand in the election.

Brand commitment can be economic, emotional, and psychological between consumers and brands. In fact, the commitment is divided into 2 parts. Commitment on a cost basis means that a person stays in a relationship because there are no more comparable options or the cost of moving on to another option is too high, which is called sustainable commitment [23] The indicators of brand commitment in the study [23](1). Emotional attachment to the brand: respondents' assessment of their emotional attachment to the brand, (2). Brand is very important, (3). Attraction to the brand, (4). Satisfaction with the brand, (5). The extent of loyalty to the brand.

3. Methodology

This study uses a quantitative approach. The type of research used in this research is a causal relationship or a cause-and-effect relationship. Causal research is research that aims to determine the cause-and-effect relationship between independent variables and dependent variables (Sugiyono, 2018). The causal relationship of this study is to reveal the analysis, brand relationship, brand personality, to brand loyalty through brand commitment to bang fish products in Medan City. The population and sample in this study were 196 respondents calculated using the Slovin formula. with independent variables consisting of: Brand Relationship, Brand Personality, dependent variables (bound) consisting of: Brand Loyalty, Mediation or Intervening (Z) variables: Brand Commitment. The data collection technique used is the questionnaire method and the data analysis technique used in this study is the SEM-PLS analysis technique (SmartPLS 4).

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

4. Result and discussion

Based on the validity test of the outer loadings in Figure 2, the variables brand relationship (X1), brand personality (X2), brand loyalty (Y), and brand commitment (Z) all have a value of > 0.7 , which means that the indicators used in this study have met the convergent validity.

4.1. Uji Hipotesis (Path Coefficient)

This test was carried out by looking at the significance to determine the influence between variables through the bootstrapping procedure. The significance value can be done by looking at the parameter coefficient and T-Statistics on the coefficient path. The research hypothesis is accepted if the T-Statistical value > 1.96 (t 5% significance table).

Table 1 Path Coefficient Test & Significance of Influence

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Brand Relationship (X2) -> Brand Loyalty (Y)	0.186	0.182	0.058	3.215	0.001
Brand Relationship (X2) -> Brand Commitment (Z)	0.250	0.246	0.073	3.597	0.000
Brand Personality (X3) -> Brand Loyalty (Y)	0.244	0.247	0.064	3.786	0.000
Brand Personality (X3) -> Brand Commitment (Z)	0.201	0.201	0.074	2.734	0.006
Brand Commitment (Z) -> Brand Loyalty (Y)	0.313	0.316	0.099	3.163	0.002

Based on the results of the path coefficient above, it can be seen that First, Brand Relationship (X2) has a positive effect on Brand Loyalty (Y) resulting in a coefficient value of 0.186 with a T-Statistic value of 3.215 > 1.96 and P Values of 0.001 < 0.05. Thus, Brand Relationship (X2) affects Brand Loyalty (Y), so the hypothesis (H1) is accepted.

Fourth, Brand Relationship (X2) has a positive effect on Brand Commitment (Z) resulting in a coefficient value of 0.250 with a T-Statistical value of 3.597 > 1.96 and P Values of 0.000 < 0.05. Thus, Brand Relationship (X2) has an effect on Brand Commitment (Z), so the hypothesis (H4) is accepted.

Fifth, Brand Personality (X3) has a positive effect on Brand Loyalty (Y) resulting in a coefficient value of 0.244 with a T-Statistical value of 3.786 > 1.96 and P Values of 0.000 < 0.05. Thus, Brand Personality (X3) affects Brand Loyalty (Y), so the hypothesis (H5) is accepted.

Sixth, Brand Personality (X3) has a positive effect on Brand Commitment (Z) resulting in a coefficient value of 0.201 with a T-Statistical value of 2.734 > 1.96 and P Values of 0.006 < 0.05. Thus, Brand Personality (X3) affects Brand Commitment (Z), so the hypothesis (H6) is accepted.

Ninth, Brand Commitment (Z) has a positive effect on Brand Loyalty (Y) resulting in a coefficient value of 0.313 with a T-Statistical value of 3.163 > 1.96 and P Values of 0.002 < 0.05. Thus, Brand Commitment (Z) affects Brand Loyalty (Y), so the hypothesis (H9) is accepted.

4.2. Indirect Effect

In the indirect effect test, it was carried out to see the influence of independent variables on dependent variables through mediating variables. In this study, it was carried out by looking at the output of specific indirect effect with a significant value of < 0.05 (p values) and a T-Statistical value of > 1.96.

Table 2 Mediation Testing

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Brand Relationship (X2) -> Brand Commitment (Z) -> Brand Loyalty (Y)	0.078	0.079	0.037	2.140	0.032
Brand Personality (X3) -> Brand Commitment (Z) -> Brand Loyalty (Y)	0.063	0.064	0.031	2.003	0.045

Based on table 2 of the indirect effect above, it can be seen that Brand Commitment (Z) significantly mediates the relationship between Brand Relationship (X2) and Brand Loyalty (Y), resulting in a coefficient value of 0.078 with T-

Statistics = 2,140 > 1.96 and P-Values = 0.032 < 0.05. Thus, the Brand Relationship variable (X2) affects the Brand loyalty variable (Y) through the Brand Commitment variable (Z) as the mediation variable, so that the mediation hypothesis (H11) is accepted.

Brand Commitment (Z) significantly mediates the relationship between Brand Personality (X3) and Brand Loyalty (Y), resulting in a coefficient value of 0.063 with T-Statistics = 2.003 > 1.96 and P-Values = 0.045 < 0.05. Thus, the variable Brand Personality (X3) berpengaruh terhadap variabel Brand loyalty (Y) melalui variabel Brand Commitment (Z) as a mediation variable, so the mediation hypothesis (H12) is accepted.

5. Conclusion

Based on the title of the research, the formulation of the problem, the purpose of the research, the hypothesis, the analysis and discussion of trialability, brand relationship, brand personality, and company reputation on brand loyalty through brand commitment to bang fish products in the city of Medan. So it can be concluded as follows:

- The R-Square value of Y is 0.816, which means that X1, X2, Z are able to explain or influence Y by 81.6%.
- The R-Square value of Z is 0.662, which means that X1, X2, is able to explain or influence Z by 66.2%.
- Brand Relationship (X2) has a positive effect on Brand Loyalty (Y) on Bang Fish product customers in Medan City.
- Brand Relationship (X2) has a positive effect on Brand Commitment (Z) on Bang Fish product customers in Medan City.
- Brand Personality (X3) has a positive effect on Brand Loyalty (Y) in Bang Fish product customers in Medan City
- Brand Personality (X3) has a positive effect on Brand Commitment (Z) on Bang Fish product customers in Medan City.
- Brand Commitment (Z) has a positive effect on Brand Loyalty (Y1) in Bang Fish product customers in Medan City.
- Brand Commitment (Z) significantly mediates the relationship between Brand Relationship (X2) and Brand Loyalty (Y) in Bang Fish products in Medan City.
- Brand Commitment (Z) significantly mediates the relationship between Brand Personality (X3) and Brand Loyalty (Y1) in Bang Fish products in Medan City.

Suggestion

Bang fish products in Medan City are able to maintain, improve and accelerate, Brand Relationship, Brand Personality, Brand Loyalty through Brand Commitment in Medan City because it has a significant influence, including loyal customers, emotional bonds, product innovation, not wanting to turn to other brands and always wanting to try new products from the bang fish brand.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

If two or more authors have contributed in the manuscript, the conflict of interest statement must be inserted here.

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